

Impact of Fixed Orthodontic Appliances on Tooth Root Integrity: A Review

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Received on: 31 August 2024; Accepted on: 02 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

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Abstract

Pathogenesis related to root resorption of different kinds involves mainly two phases i.e. injury caused chemically or mechanically of the protecting tissue and stimulation of tissue produced by the infection or the pressure applied. Identification of the etiology of root resorption is helpful in delivering the correct treatment by removing the factors.

Keywords: Root Resorption, Tooth Movement, Orthodontic Therapy

Introduction

Resorption of the apical root is a frequent elementary issue connected to orthodontic therapy and has always attracted a lot of attention from clinicians. It is very difficult to predict the loss of apical root and it becomes irreversible when it reaches the layer of dentin. The majority of root loss brought on by orthodontic treatment does not reduce the long life or the ability of teeth to function. Individual vulnerability, genetic predisposition, systemic or local, and various anatomical aspects related to orthodontic treatment are frequently mentioned elements¹. In 1885, Root resorption related to permanent teeth was first talked about by Bates². Similarly, in 1914, root resorption has a direct relation to orthodontic treatment was said by Ottolengui³. The alteration between the shape of the root seen before and after the orthodontic mechanotherapy was demonstrated by Ketcham on the basis of radiographs^{4,5}. Following this, several studies focusing on the histology, physiology, and clinical aspect of root resorption and its relation to orthodontic treatment were conducted.

Throughout the literature pertaining to the loss of apical root material, the two words were brought to use alternately⁶ that are “resorption” and “absorption”.

- Root resorption process

Permanent tooth root resorption is a complicated biologic process with numerous unresolved variables. Physiologic tooth movement, pressure from the neighboring tooth which is impacted, periapical or inflammation of the periodontium, tooth implantation or replantation, occlusal trauma constant in nature, tumors or cysts,

metabolic or systemic disturbances, local functional or behavioral related problems, orthodontic treatment, and factors of unknown origin are a few of the major causes in the permanent teeth to cause root resorption listed by Phillips, Reitan, and Shafer et al^{7,8,9}.

Three forms of external root resorption are listed in Andreasen-

- Surface resorption
- Inflammatory resorption
- Transient inflammatory resorption
- Progressive inflammatory resorption
- Replacement resorption

After the accomplishment of the orthodontic treatment, the root resorption seen is the surface resorption or transient inflammatory resorption. Replacement resorption is hardly seen after the completion of the orthodontic treatment^{10,11}. Underlying bone from the cementum which is parted by the periodontal layer is affected equally by orthodontic forces. If these two organs behaved biologically identically, they would both resorb in an equal amount. However, it is seen that cementum is much more resistant to the resorption by the forces in comparison with the bone, therefore, the tooth moves as a result of the forces being applied, which mostly results in bone resorption. Still, it is seen that Cementum and dentin resorption can also happen. Similar cytologic and functional traits are shared by the osteoclast and the root resorbing cell, or odontoclast.

How to cite this article: Saini et al. - Impact of Fixed Orthodontic Appliances on Tooth Root Integrity: A Review HTAJ OCD 2024

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

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Few published articles have shown that resorption activities in reciprocation to the mechanical and chemicals stimulation by the cells of the periodontal ligament are mainly characterized by the synthesizing prostaglandin E and with increased cAMP¹². It has been proposed that osteoblasts in many ways control the osteoclast's cells. There are several hypotheses that explain why dental tissues are resistant to resorption, particularly cemental resistance. According to and reason, the periodontal ligament's innermost cellular layer is related to surface resistance. The root is protected by this layer, which also offers the possibility of repair¹⁰. This layer consists of perivascular, endothelial, fibroblast, osteoblast, cementoblast, and fibroblast cells. The curing of greater zones of injury which may cause ankylosis is related to the alveolar bone and bone marrow-derived cells. Osteoid, pre-cementum, and predentin, which are uncalcified mineral tissues, have been shown to be resorption-resistant and to be able to temporarily stop the depletion of the tissue of root. But continued pressure in due course will cause these areas to resorb^{8,11}. It has been asserted that orthodontic root resorption takes place in the same regions where physiologic root resorption begins¹³.

During orthodontic treatment, periodontal hyalinization occurs before root resorption. This area's neighboring and contiguous areas experience root material loss. The hyalinized zone divides its life cycle into three stages: degeneration, product elimination, and re-establishment. The procedure for resorbing roots is connected to the removal of hyalinized tissue. The hyalinized zone divides its life cycle into three stages:

- Degeneration
- Product elimination
- Reestablishment.

The procedure for resorbing roots is connected to the removal of hyalinized tissue¹⁴. Resorbed lacunae can take¹⁰ to 35 days to emerge after the application of force. Clinically, radiographs are unable to show this level of resorption, specifically when it affects the buccal and lingual surfaces. If the applied pressure is decreased below the range of 20 to 26g/cm² of force the root resorption is seen to be increased. It is said that resorbed lacunae are occupied by the cementoid. This procedure starts the healing process while delaying the onset of fresh root resorption. 35 to 70 days following the application of force, the resorption of lacunae is repaired^{15,16}.

Influencing factors for root resorption

- **Biological factor**

Individual susceptibility

With or without orthodontic therapy, individual sensitivity is thought to be a significant factor in determining the risk for root resorption. Rygh claims that the process of the resorption of the root appears to differ between the people and even within a single individual over time. Hormones, the type of the body, and metabolic rate are among the metabolic signals that affect how osteoblastic and osteoclastic activity is correlated with one another¹⁴.

Genetics

Numerous studies overwhelmingly support the genetic basis of shorter roots. Autosomal dominant, autosomal

recessive, and polygenic modes of inheritance are possible but no final conclusion was founded¹⁷.

Systemic factors

As per the Becks, root resorption is associated with endocrine conditions such as hypothyroidism, hypopituitarism, hyperpituitarism, and other illnesses.

Nutrition

Malnutrition, according to Marshall, can lead to root resorption¹⁹.

Chronologic age

All tissues involved in the process of resorption of the root change in the company of aging. The cementum widens, the bone becomes more dense, avascular, and aplastic, and the periodontal membrane becomes less vascular, aplastic, and narrow. Adults have a higher sensitivity to root resorption, which reflects these changes. Investigations were done on the connections between resorption of the root, orthodontic therapy, and the age of the patient. Root resorption is more common in adulthood, as evidenced by the frequently reported positive correlation between both variables. Only a few studies revealed no association between patient's age at the time of orthodontic therapy and apical root loss²⁰.

The presence of root resorption before orthodontics

There is a strong connection in the quantity and severity of root resorption existing prior to treatment and the root resorption was located after the removal of the orthodontic appliance²⁰.

Tooth structure

Root resorption after the orthodontic therapy is more probable to happen in roots with a deviation in shape. High root resorption potential is thought to be indicated by convergent apical root canals²¹.

Previously traumatized teeth

The exterior root resorption of traumatized teeth can occur without orthodontic intervention. Traumatized teeth that have undergone root resorption and have been orthodontically repositioned are more susceptible to additional root material loss. Following orthodontic treatment, in comparison to untraumatized teeth, patients with trauma had a root loss almost of 1.07 mm as compared to 0.64 mm²².

Endodontically treated teeth

Endodontically treated teeth has been observed to undergo root resorption during orthodontic therapy frequently and with greater severity. The increased dentin hardness and density in endodontically treated teeth may, however, make them more resilient to root resorption.

- **Mechanical factor**

Appliances

It is frequently said that the type of equipment used determines the extent of root damage. A single study evaluated the resorption of the root brought on by fixed and removable appliances, and it came to the conclusion that the usage of fixed appliances is more destructive to the roots²². Edgewise versus light wire Begg: It is frequently said that the edgewise technique results in more root resorption²⁵. While Malmgren et al. claimed that there has been no alteration between both approaches, so they discovered that when the Begg technique was used to intrude on traumatized maxillary

incisors compared to the edgewise technique, root resorption was significantly more common²⁶.

Intermaxillary elastics

Linge and Linge discovered that the side with elastics had considerably more root resorption, and they hypothesized that the incisor's root resorption was caused by jiggling pressures brought on by function paired with elastics²². First molar distal root resorption in the mandible was made worse by Class III elastics utilized for anchoring preparation²⁷.

Extraction

Contrasting serial extractions without orthodontic treatment with serial extractions with orthodontic therapy, or with the removal of four premolars and then fixed appliance therapy, serial extractions without orthodontic therapy produced a comparatively lesser amount of root resorption.

Continuous vs intermittent forces

Intermittent forces during a treatment break allow the resorbed cementum to repair and stop further resorption²⁸. On the contrary, forces that are intermittent and jiggling forces have been seen to be connected in terms of their negative impacts.

- **Biological and mechanical elements combined**

Treatment duration: According to the majority of research, the length of treatment has a direct impact on how severe root resorption is. According to Rudolph¹, 2, 3, and 7 years later with active orthodontic treatment, that 40%, 70%, 80%, and 100% of the patients in treatment showcased some resorption of root, respectively²⁹. According to Goldin, 0.9 mm/year of the root mass is lost during treatment³⁰.

Relapse: It was believed that the forces of relapse are insufficient to result in root resorption¹³. Ten Hoeve and Mulie, on the hand, think that mild muscular pressures during relapse make the teeth more vulnerable to further root loss³¹.

• **Root resorption after appliance removal:** In terms of orthodontic treatment, root resorption often stopped once the active treatment was finished, Considering that increasing root resorption is impacted by tissue pressure¹¹. After the removal of the appliance, According to Reitan, there is an extra-active resorption phase that lasts for about a week, followed by a period of orthodontic inactivity of 5 to 6 weeks as the cementum heals⁸.

- **Root resorption diagnostic tools**

A frequent diagnostic tool for root resorption is radiography. A certain amount of resorption is necessary for the radiographic identification of apical root shortening³². Assessing the precise amount of root loss is more challenging while the tooth is moving, particularly when it is being torqued or pointed. Common radiographs are unhelpful for identifying the resorption of the buccal and lingual roots. The periapical bisecting angle, periapical paralleling, orthopantomogram, and cephalogram are among the radiographic methods used³³. The periapical paralleling approach, despite its drawbacks, provides the best benefit-to-risk ratio when it comes to identifying and assessing the extent of loss of the material of the root apically³⁴. Comparing the periapical approach to the orthopantomogram or the lateral headfilm, the former offers less distortion and superimposition faults.

Conclusion

All permanent teeth may have minute quantities of radiographically undetectable and clinically inconsequential root resorption. Active tooth movement and orthodontic therapy may lead to permanent tooth root resorption. Researchers have documented varying amounts of root resorption during orthodontic therapy. When exposed to a variety of stimuli, teeth that are permanent have the ability to clinically experience severe exterior root resorption. This resorptive capability varies from individual to individual and from one tooth to another within the same person. Therefore, clinicians should consider all factors while making the diagnosis and selecting the course of treatment³⁵.

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